

USING MIND MAP IN ENGLISH LESSONS AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5830476>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th December 2021

Accepted: 25th December 2021

Online: 30th December 2021

KEY WORDS

mind map, method, problem, discussion, learning, teaching, conversation, developing creative thinking.

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the use of mind map method in English lessons as foreign language. The stages of application, advantages and disadvantages are explained.

INTRODUCTION

In foreign language lessons many methods for learning new themes are used. For example fishbowl, mind map, at stations learning and others. A mind map is a visual record of new vocabulary, or other content. Vocabulary mind maps are also known as word maps or spider grams, and are organized in a way that shows groupings or relationships between the words. The teacher writes a list of words based around the topic of food on the board. Learners organize the words in a mind map and then compare ideas on how they have grouped words and related them. In the classroom Mind maps are often used as a tool in the planning stage for writing exercises, as learners can structure ideas and discuss how they are related.

MAIN PART

Mind mapping is a learning technique which uses a non-linear approach to learning that forces the learner to think and explore concepts using visual-spatial relationships flowing from a central theme to peripheral branches which can be inter-related.

How do you do a mind map in English?

How To Create a Mind Map?

1. Create a Central Idea. The central idea is the starting point of your Mind Map and represents the topic you are going to explore. ...
2. Add branches to your map. ...
3. Add keywords. ...
4. Color code your branches. ...
5. Include visual signifiers (e.g. images)

A mind map, or spidergram, is a strategy for making notes on a topic, prior to writing. It is a structured strategy, which

shows the (hierarchical) relationship of ideas, as opposed to an unstructured strategy, such as brainstorming, in which students produce notes at random on paper.

Having an organized display of information from the outset of the writing process may help some students, as it is more easily converted into a draft, whereas in brainstorming, the random recording of ideas might lead to problems with the structure of students' texts.

The advantages of mind maps

Making a mind map should be a spontaneous pre-writing activity. Students start with a topic at the center and then generate a web of ideas from that, developing and relating these ideas as their mind makes associations.

Mind maps work well as their visual design enables students to see the relationship between ideas, and encourages them to group certain ideas together as they proceed. Mind maps work especially well when created in groups, since the discussion this engenders aids the production of ideas, and makes the task livelier and more enjoyable.

How to make mind maps with your students:

1. Choosing a topic

Traditionally, students are given a topic to write on by the teacher. However, with certain classes, students may prefer to nominate the topic themselves. This can lead to greater interest in the task on the part of the student, as well as, perhaps, greater knowledge of the topic under study.

The mind map strategy can be used to explore almost any topic, though discursive essays and narrative work particularly well as they front students' ideas and lend them to discussing ideas in groups.

We usually start by writing the topic on the board. In the last writing class we taught, with a group of upper-intermediate students, I chose a discursive essay with the title "Why do people start smoking?" I chose this genre as we had recently been looking at the language used to give reasons and explanations. The discursive text is useful in highlighting this feature of English, and in raising awareness of the noun phrase, a particularly tricky area for intermediate students.

2. Note making

Once the topic has been introduced, we encourage my students to close their eyes and think about it for a minute or two, in silence. They then have two minutes in which to note down their ideas. If they do not know a word in English, they can write it in L1 at this stage, as dictionaries or too much teacher intervention tend to halt and inhibit the creative flow.

Then, working in groups, they can compare and discuss their ideas, perhaps adding to their mind maps as they go. This stage also provides the opportunity for peer teaching, as other students may be available to provide the English word for the idea that was noted down in L1.

DISCUSSION

The next stage, in which the teacher makes a collective mind map on the board, is optional, but is useful for students who are new to the idea of mind maps, or for weak classes. It is also in this feedback stage that any remaining language problems can be ironed out. As the teacher elicits students' ideas, and reformulates expressions or corrects, students will learn how to express their ideas in English. Such personalization is said to aid vocabulary learning.

The map is fluid and changeable, and new connections or subgroups can be made, or branches added, as the students make suggestions. The end result should be an organized display of information, showing the central topic, and a number of subtopics and further points that stem from it.

Organizing mind maps

In the next stage the students organize their mind maps into a linear format to decide the best way in which to present their points. They should first think about the overall structure, i.e. the order in which to relay the information, and then focus on the precise function each paragraph will have in their final text, as this helps to clarify their writing. This can be done in groups or as a class with the teacher leading the discussion.

However it is carried out, it is important to provide a context and audience. We told my class, who were writing about drugs, that they were writing for their college magazine. Having an audience in mind helps students to decide which ideas are most important, and also helps students to choose the appropriate style.

RESULT

Writing

Students should then begin to write their compositions, working in pairs if they wish. After two paragraphs, they should exchange their compositions, so they become readers of each other's work. This allows for feedback, and possible re-writing. Once they have finished, they should again exchange their texts. This gives their texts a communicative purpose, as well as developing an awareness of the fact that a writer is always producing something to be read by someone else, rather than for the display of writing alone.

Continuation

Once students are familiar with the idea of making mind maps, they can be encouraged to use this skill for further writing activities. It is a useful technique and often improves the clarity and organization of student texts.

CONCLUSION

Using mind map in English as foreign language lessons are very useful for creative thinking of students. Mind map can be used for every theme and teacher can know how knowledge of students in this theme is. Mind map is useful for remembering new words too.

REFERENCES:

1. Shokhistakhon N. USING FISHBOWL METHOD IN ENGLISH LESSONS AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE //ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 06. – C. 310-314.
<https://reserchjet.academiascience.org/index.php/rjai/article/download/293/27>
Q Murojaat sanasi 09.12.2021
2. Нуралиева Ш. А. Чет тилларни ўқитишда дидактика тушунчаси //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 1081-1086.
<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/chet-tillarni-itishda-didaktika-tushunchasi>
Murojaat sanasi: 09.12.2021

3. Edwards S., Cooper N. Mind mapping as a teaching resource //The clinical teacher. – 2010. – T. 7. – №. 4. – C. 236-239.
4. Mento A. J., Martinelli P., Jones R. M. Mind mapping in executive education: applications and outcomes //Journal of Management Development. – 1999.